

Study on Prescribing Pattern of Drugs and Rationality of Prescription in Patients Attending Outpatient Departments of Tertiary Care Hospital at Rewa, Madhya Pradesh, India

Pathak V^{1*}, Patidar A², Singh P³, Singh B⁴, Tiwari RN⁵, Chaturvedi JN^{6*}

¹Resident, Department of Pharmacology, Shyam Shah Medical College, Rewa (M.P)

²Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Shyam Shah Medical College, Rewa (M.P)

³Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Shyam Shah Medical College Rewa (M.P)

⁴Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Government Medical College Satna (M.P)

⁵Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Shyam Shah Medical College, Rewa (M.P)

⁶Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Government Medical College Satna (M.P)

Received: 25-10-2023 / Revised: 23-11-2023 / Accepted: 26-12-2023

Corresponding Author: Dr. Chaturvedi JN

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Pharmacotherapy has been the mainstay of treatment since ages. Drug prescription pattern studies not only gives an insight to current trends of diseases that are commonly encountered in day today practice but also forms the basis of modifications in drug policies and rational use of medicines. The present study was aimed to describe the prescription pattern and rationality of various drugs and in patients attending the OPDs of various clinical specialties. Data regarding prescription was collected randomly in the prospective manner of 1000 outdoor patients visiting the tertiary care hospital affiliated to Medical College. Prescription of various groups, classes and individual drugs are described in percentage. The rationality of prescription was also analyzed by using WHO/INRUD core indicators of prescription. Vitamins were the most frequently prescribed class of drugs (18.1%) followed by NSAIDs (17.1%). Polypharmacy and frequent prescription of antimicrobials was a major concern found in this study. 98.1% of total prescribed drugs were by their generic name and were from NLEM, 2022. More judicious use of drugs, especially antimicrobials, will help in improving the rational use of medicines.

Keywords: Prescription Patten, Rational Use Of Medicines, Polypharmacy, WHO/INRUD Core Indicators.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Drugs play an important role in restoring, maintaining and protecting the health of an individual. Prescription writing is a science and an art, as it conveys the message from the prescriber to the patient. The treatment of diseases by the use of essential drugs, prescribed by their generic names, has been emphasized by the WHO and National Health Policy of India. [1] Irrational use of Medicine is a worldwide issue, therefore WHO is advocating rational use of Medicines.

Worldwide, half of the medicines are prescribed, dispensed or sold improperly and half of the patients fail to take them correctly. Moreover, about one third of the world's population lacks access to essential medicine. [2] Many developing countries have an essential drug list with the aim to achieve availability and affordability of drug therapy at various levels of health care. However, the quality of care delivered to patients depends on giving the right drugs, for correct indications, in a

way that encourages the patient to take the medications. [3] Drug utilization research holds a crucial place in clinical practice as it forms the basis for making amendments in the drug dispensing policies at local and national levels. The ultimate goal of such research is to facilitate rational drug use. [4]

So, this study was conducted to describe the current trend of prescription patterns of various drugs prescribed to patients attending outdoors of various clinical specialty departments in a tertiary care hospital at Rewa, Madhya Pradesh, India. Also, this study was intended to analyze the prescriptions as per WHO/INRUD guidelines using core group indicators of prescription.

Methods

After getting the approval from the Institutional Ethics Committee dated 08.01.2021, the study was

carried over a period of one year from July, 2021 to June, 2022.

Study Design: Cross Sectional Study.

Inclusion Criteria: Prescriptions for allopathic medicines.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Prescriptions with non-pharmacotherapy advice only.
- Prescriptions for vaccination only.

After informed consent from patient/guardian, photocopies of 1000 prescriptions were randomly collected from the patient/guardian visiting the pharmacy of affiliated hospitals after their consultation from outdoors of various clinical speciality departments of Shyam Shah Medical College, Rewa (M.P.).

All prescriptions were analyzed for demographic details; pattern of prescribed classes of drugs and individual drug and WHO core drug use indicators as per following WHO/INRUD prescribing drug indicators:

- Average number of medicines prescribed per patient.
- Percentage of medicines prescribed by generic names.
- Percentage of encounters with an antibiotic prescribed.
- Percentage of injections prescribed.
- Percentage of medicines prescribed from essential drug lists. (EDL)

The above collected data are presented as percentage and average. No statistical hypotheses were tested.

Results and Discussion

A total of 1000 prescriptions which contained a total 3110 drug or drug combinations were collected and analyzed during this study. Most of the patients attending the OPDs (25%) were between the age group of 21-30 years. The distribution of various outpatients was almost similar for males (45.3%) and females (54.7%).

Maximum number of prescriptions were from general medicine (26.9%) followed by dermatology (14%) and orthopedics (13%) departments. (Fig. 1)

Major Classes of drugs prescribed are shown in Fig.2. Most prescribed drugs were vitamins and minerals (27.4%) followed by drugs acting on the autacoid system (23.0); GIT (21%) and antimicrobials (17.4%). In a study by Hussain S et al., the most common group of drugs prescribed was drugs acting on gastrointestinal tract (26.38%) followed by vitamins & minerals (23.12%) and drugs acting on cardiovascular system (11.56%). [5] In another study by Bhavesh K. Lalan et al., the

most common group of drugs prescribed was vitamins & minerals (24.44%) followed by analgesics (17.76%) and antimicrobials (16.59%). [6] In another study by Tripathi JP et al. Antimicrobials were prescribed in 45.3% of prescriptions followed by vitamins (34.8%) and Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (33.9%). [7]

Frequency of major groups and classes of various drugs prescribed are shown in Table 1. Among various classes of drugs frequency of individually prescribed drugs are shown in Table 2. Among vitamins & minerals the most commonly prescribed was vitamin B complex (62.7%) followed by calcium supplements (20.2%). In a study by Mohanty BK et al., 66.61% of prescriptions contained at least one multivitamin or iron. [8]

Among drugs acting on autacoid system, NSAIDs (74.3%) was the most frequently prescribed class of drug followed by antihistaminics (25.7%), of which ibuprofen+paracetamol prescription constitutes 43.1% followed by cetirizine 22.6%, diclofenac 14.1% and paracetamol 13.7% of all prescribed drugs in this broad group. In a study by R Vaishnavi et al., NSAIDs were prescribed in 30.83% of encounters and the most frequently prescribed NSAID was paracetamol (39.45%) [9].

Among drugs acting on the gastrointestinal system, the most commonly prescribed class of drugs were anti peptic ulcer drugs, of which pantoprazole constitutes 60% of total prescribed drugs that act on GIT. In a study by Madi L et al., esomeprazole and pantoprazole were most frequently prescribed proton pump inhibitors (34% and 31% respectively). [10]

Among antimicrobials, the most commonly prescribed class of drugs were beta lactams, of which Amoxicillin+clavulanic acid constitutes 16.2% prescriptions followed by cefixime 14.7% of total antimicrobials prescribed. In a study by Sanmukhpriya S et al., out of 138 antimicrobials prescribed 22.5% were of cefuroxime, 11.6% were of azithromycin, 11.5% were of cefixime. [6]. Another study by Bilal AI et al., of total 1426 medicines prescribed, 49.6% were antibiotics, with amoxicillin (33.3%) and co-trimoxazole (16.0%) being the most frequently prescribed agents. [11]

Among the drugs acting on endocrine system, glucocorticoids were most frequently prescribed (65.3%) followed by antidiabetic agents (19.8%), of which mometasone cream (45.4%), prednisolone (11.6%) and metformin (10.7%) respectively were the most frequently prescribed drugs.

Among the drugs acting on the cardiovascular system, anti-hypertensive agents (98.3%) constitute the entire prescriptions analyzed followed by anti-arrhythmic agents (1.7%). Among the antihypertensives, angiotensin receptor blockers/

combinations (35.1%) followed by calcium channel blockers (22.8%) were most frequently prescribed classes, of which telmisartan (31.6%) and amlodipine (22.8%) were the most frequently prescribed drugs. In a study by Dutta S et al., calcium channel blockers/ combinations (72.3%) were the most frequently prescribed antihypertensive class, of which amlodipine (55.6%) was the most frequently prescribed drug. [12] Among the drugs acting on central nervous system, antiepileptics (27.8%) followed by central acting anticholinergic agent (20.9%) were the most frequently prescribed classes, of which trihexyphenidyl (20.9%) and sodium valproate (11.3%) were the most frequently prescribed drugs.

Analysis of prescriptions as per WHO/INRUD core drug prescription indicator is shown in Table 3. In this study, among total 1000 prescriptions, 3110 drug/combinations were prescribed with the average of 3.1 drugs per prescription found; the ideal range is 1.6-1.8. The number of medicines prescribed by generic name was found to 98.1% (3050/3110), ideal value is 100%. The Number of encounters with an antibiotic prescribed was 41.6% (416/1000), the ideal range being 20-26.8%. The number of encounters with an injectable preparation prescribed was 1% (10/1000), the ideal range is 13.4-24.1%. Number of drugs prescribed from the national EDL is 98.4% (3059/3110), the ideal value is 100%. In a study conducted by Yimer YS et al.; on average, 1.95 drugs were prescribed per prescription. Percentage of encounters by generic name, encounters with antibiotics and injection, and drugs from essential drug list were 99.9%, 35.4%, 15.3%, and 100%, respectively. [13]

In another study by Shanmugapriya S et al.; A total of 700 prescriptions were analyzed and the average number of drugs per prescription was 2.955 ± 1.32 . Amongst the prescribing indicators, generic prescribing was appallingly low (6.42%). In contrast, antibiotic prescribing and prescription of injections showed an appreciably rational trend with 15.42% and 8.14%, respectively. Furthermore, the prescription of the drugs enlisted in the essential drugs list was determined to be 90.67%. [6]

In another study by Shrestha R et al.; Out of total 770 prescriptions, The average number of drugs per encounter was 3.2. The percentage of encounters with antibiotic and injection was 37.9% (n = 292) and 0.7% (n = 5), respectively. The percentage of drugs prescribed by generic and from an essential medicine list of Nepal was 2.9% (n = 72) and 21.3% (n = 521), respectively. [14]

In a study by Atif M et al.; Amongst the prescribing indicators, the average number of drugs per prescription was 2.8 (SD = 1.3), the drugs prescribed by generic name were 56.6 %, the

encounters with an antibiotic prescribed were 51.5%, no injections were prescribed and 98.8% of the drugs prescribed were from the Essential Drugs List (EDL). [15] In another Study by Ofori-Adjei YA et al.; Out of 678 prescriptions The average number of drugs prescribed per encounter was 4.4, drugs prescribed by generic name was 86.9%, patient encounters in which antibiotics prescribed were 6.5% (n= 44) and injections were prescribed in 3.2% (n=22) of patient encounters. 64.0% of all drugs prescribed were from the Ghanaian EML. [16]

In a study by Summoro TS et al.; out of 1440 prescriptions, the average number of drugs per prescription was found to be in the range of 1.82 ± 0.90 to 2.28 ± 0.90 . The percentage of drugs prescribed by generic name was 95.8%. Percentage use of injectables was found to be 15 to 61.7. Drugs prescribed from the essential drug list was found to be 94.1%. [17]

In a Study carried by Hussain S et al.; Out of 1000 prescriptions, the average number of drugs per prescription was 2.91. The percentage of drugs prescribed by generic name, from the essential drug list (National) and as fixed dose combinations (FDCs) was 10.05%, 22.57%, and 49.22%, respectively. The total percentage of encounters with antibiotics, injectables, and FDCs was 19.70%, 2.20%, and 73.60%, respectively. [5]

In another Study by Tripathy JP et al.; Out of 1609 prescriptions, on an average, 2.2 drugs were prescribed per patient. Nearly 84% of the drugs were prescribed from the essential drug list (EDL). Antibiotics were prescribed in 45.3% of prescriptions, followed by vitamins (34.8%) and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (33.9%). Drugs were prescribed in their generic names in 70% of cases. [18]

In a Study by Bilal AI et al.; Out of 636 prescriptions, the average number of medicines per prescription was 2.2 with standard deviation of 0.8. The proportion of medicines prescribed by generic name was 97 and 92% of the prescribed medicines were included in List of Essential Medicines for Ethiopia, Prescriptions containing antibiotics and injections constituted (82.5 and 11.2%) respectively. Of the total of 1426 medicines prescribed, 49.6% were antibiotics. [6]

In a study by Ata M et al.; Out of 300 prescriptions, the average no of drugs per encounter was 3.7 and Drugs by generic name were 42.7%. Encounters with an antibiotic prescribed 34.4%. Encounter with an injection prescribed 4%. Drug prescribed from essential drug list 94%. [19]

In a study by Bhavesh K. Lalan et al.; average no of drugs per encounter was 3.62. Drugs prescribed from the essential drug list were 81.6%. Total no of

prescriptions with an antibiotic was 46.17%. Total no. of prescriptions with an injection was 0.17%.

Total number of prescriptions with an FDC was 46.67%. [7]

Table 1: Frequency of prescription of major groups and classes of various drugs

Major Group	Classes	Number Prescribed (%)
Vitamins and minerals		852 (27.4)
	Vitamins	563 (66.1)
	Minerals ± Vitamins	289 (33.9)
Drugs acting on Autacoid system		717 (23.1)
	NSAIDs	533 (74.3)
	Antihistaminics	184 (25.7)
Drugs acting on GIT		652 (21.0)
	Anti-peptic-ulcer	496 (76.1)
	Antacids	58 (8.9)
	Antiemetics	47 (7.2)
	Antispasmodics	34 (5.2)
	Laxatives	17 (2.6)
Antimicrobials		543 (17.4)
	Beta lactams	223 (41.1)
	Antifungals	91 (16.7)
	Quinolones	73 (13.4)
	Macrolides	38 (7.0)
	Tetracyclines	32 (5.9)
	Antiamoebic	24 (4.4)
	Lincosamide	17 (3.1)
	Antihelminthic	12 (2.2)
	Oxazolidinones	03 (0.5)
	Urinary antiseptic	01 (0.2)
Drugs acting on Endocrine system		121 (3.9)
	Corticosteroids	79 (65.3)
	Antidiabetics	24 (19.8)
	Estrogens±Progestins	09 (7.4)
	Thyroxine preparations	05 (4.1)
	SERM	03 (2.5)
	Antiandrogen	01 (0.8)
Drugs acting on CNS		115 (3.7)
	Antiepileptics	32 (27.8)
	Antipsychotics	24 (20.9)
	Antiparkinsonian	24 (20.9)
	Antianxiety	14 (12.1)
	Antidepressants	13 (11.3)
	Cognition enhancer	03 (2.6)
	Antimanic	02 (1.7)
	Opioid analgesics	02 (1.7)
Drugs acting on CVS		58 (1.9)
	Antihypertensives	57 (98.3)
	Antiarrhythmics	01 (1.7)
Drugs acting on Respiratory system		52 (1.6)
	Anti-asthmatic/COPD	30 (57.7)
	Cough suppressant	22 (42.3)
Total		3110 (100)

Table 2: Frequency of prescription of various classes and individual drugs

Classes	Drug	Number Prescribed (%) [N=3110]
Vitamins		563 (18.1)
	Vit. B Complex	534 (94.8)
	Vit. D	10 (1.8)
	Vit. C	08 (1.4)
	Vt. E	07 (1.3)

	Folic Acid	04 (0.7)
NSAIDs		533 (17.1)
	Ibuprofen + Paracetamol	309 (58.0)
	Diclofenac	101 (18.9)
	Paracetamol	98 (18.4)
	Aspirin	14 (2.6)
	Diclofenac + Paracetamol	07 (1.3)
	Acceclofenac + Paracetamol	03 (0.6)
	Piroxicam	01 (0.2)
Anti-peptic Ulcer		496 (15.9)
	Pantoprazole	391 (78.8)
	Ranitidine	104 (21.0)
	Sucralfate	01 (0.2)
Antihistaminics		184 (5.9)
	Cetirizine	162 (88.0)
	Levocetirizine	22 (12.0)
Minerals		182 (5.8)
	Calcium	172 (94.5)
	Iron	10 (5.5)
Cephalosporins		125 (4.0)
	Cefixime	80 (64.0)
	Cefpodoxime	44 (35.2)
	Cefuroxime	01 (0.8)
Combination of Vitamins & Minerals		107 (3.4)
	Calcium + Vit. D	65 (60.7)
	Iron + Folic acid	42 (39.3)
Penicillins		98 (3.1)
	Amoxicillin + Clavulanic acid	88 (89.8)
	Amoxicillin	09 (9.2)
	Benzathine penicillin	01 (1.0)
Antifungals		91 (2.9)
	Clotrimazole	44 (48.3)
	Fluconazole	42 (46.2)
	Ketoconazole	04 (4.4)
	Itraconazole	01 (1.1)
Glucocorticosteroids		79 (2.5)
	Mometasone	55 (69.5)
	Prednisolone	14 (17.7)
	Triamcinolone	04 (5.1)
	Fluticasone	03 (3.8)
	Dexamethasone	01 (1.3)
	Clobetasol	01 (1.3)
	Budesonide + Formoterol	01 (1.3)
Fluroquinolones ± other drugs		73 (2.3)
	Moxifloxacin	34 (46.6)
	Levofloxacin	12 (16.4)
	Ciprofloxacin	10 (13.7)
	Ofloxacin + Ornidazole	10 (13.7)
	Ofloxacin	04 (5.5)
	Ciprofloxacin + Dexamethasone	02 (2.7)
	Ofloxacin + Betamethasone	01 (1.4)
Antacids		58 (1.9)
	Magaldrate	58 (100.0)
Antiemetics		47 (1.5)
	Ondansetron	41 (87.2)
	Domperidone	06 (12.8)

Macrolides		38 (1.2)
	Azithromycin	38 (100.0)
Aminoglycosides		34 (1.1)
	Neomycin	10 (34.5)
	Tobramycin	09 (31.1)
	Tobramycin + Dexamethasone	05 (17.2)
	Tobramycin	05 (17.2)
	Framyceitin	05 (17.2)
Antispasmodics		34 (1.1)
	Dicyclomine	34 (100.0)
Tetracyclines		32 (1.0)
	Doxycycline	32 (100.0)
Antiepileptics		32 (1.0)
	Sod. Valproate	13 (40.6)
	Clonazepam	11 (34.4)
	Phenytoin	03 (9.4)
	Pregabalin	02 (6.2)
	Carbamazepine	01 (3.1)
	Phenobarbitone	01 (3.1)
	Gabapentin	01 (3.1)
Antiamoebics		24 (0.8)
	Metronidazole	22 (91.7)
	Secnidazole	02 (8.3)
Antidiabetics		24 (0.77)
	Metromin	13 (54.1)
	Metformin + Vildagliptin	07 (29.1)
	Glimepiride	01 (4.2)
	Sitagliptin	01 (4.2)
	Vildagliptin	01 (4.2)
	Metformin + Glimepiride	01 (4.2)
Antipsychotics		24 (0.77)
	Risperidone	12 (50.0)
	Olanzapine	09 (37.5)
	Flupenthixol + Melitracen	03 (12.5)
	Clozapine	01 (4.2)
Central anticholinergics		24 (0.77)
	Trihexyphenidyl	24 (100.0)
Antitussive		22 (0.7)
	Dextromethorphan	22 (100.0)
Leukotriene antagonist		22 (0.7)
	Montelukast	22 (100.0)
ARBs		18 (0.6)
	Telmisartan	18 (100.0)
Laxatives		17 (0.5)
	Lactulose	15 (88.2)
	Liquid Paraffin	02 (11.8)
Lincosamides		17 (0.5)
	Clindamycin	17 (100.0)
Antianxiety		14 (0.4)
	Alprazolam	07 (50.0)
	Lorazepam	07 (50.0)
Antidepressants		13 (0.4)
	Amitriptyline	10 (76.9)
	Escitalopram	03 (13.1)
CCBs		13 (0.4)
	Amlodipine	13 (100.0)
Antihelminthics		12 (0.4)

	Albendazole	08 (66.7)
	Ivermectin	04 (33.3)
Beta blockers		11 (0.35)
	Propranolol	05 (45.5)
	Metoprolol	05 (45.5)
	Bisoprolol	01 (9.0)
Bronchodilators		08 (0.3)
	Etophylline + Theophylline	04 (50.0)
	Salbutamol	01 (12.5)
	Levosalbutamol	01 (12.5)
	Etophylline	01 (12.5)
	Salbutamol + Ambroxol	01 (12.5)
Progestins		07 (0.3)
	Medroxyprogesterone	03 (42.8)
	Norethisterone	03 (42.8)
	Progesterone	02 (28.6)
ACEIs		07 (0.3)
	Ramipril	07 (100.0)
Diuretics		06 (0.2)
	Furosemide	04 (66.7)
	Furosemide + Spironolactone	02 (33.3)
Thyroxine analogue		05 (0.2)
	Levothyroxine	05 (100)
Oxazolidinones		03 (0.1)
	Linezolid	03 (100.0)
SERM		03 (0.1)
	Tamoxifen	03 (100)
Cognition enhancers		03 (0.1)
	Piracetam	02 (66.7)
	Donepezil	01 (33.3)
Antimanic		02 (0.06)
	Lithium	02 (100.0)
Opioid Analgesic		02 (0.06)
	Tramadol	02 (100.0)
ARBs Combination		02 (0.06)
	Telmisartan + Hydrochlorothiazide	02 (100.0)
Urinary Antiseptics		01 (0.03)
	Nitrofurantoin	01 (100.0)
Combined Oral Contraceptives		01 (0.03)
	Ethinylestradiol + Levonorgestrel	01 (100.0)
5 α reductase inhibitors		01 (0.03)
	Dutasteride	01 (100.0)
Antiarrhythmic		01 (0.03)
	Amiodarone	01 (100.0)
Total		3110 (100)

Table 3: Analysis of prescriptions as per WHO/INRUD core drug prescription indicator

S. No.	Parameter	Observation	Optimal/Ideal Value (%)
1.	Average Number of Drugs Per Prescription	3.1 (3110/1000)	1.6-1.8
2.	Number of Drugs Prescribed by Generic name	98.1% (3050/3110)	100
3.	Number of Encounters with an Antibiotic Prescribed	41.6% (416/1000)	20-26.8
4.	Number of Encounters with an Injectable Preparation Prescribed	1% (10/1000)	13.4-24.1
5.	No of Medicines Prescribed from National List of Essential Medicines, 2022	98.4% (3049/3110)	100

Figure 1: Clinical Specialties wise distribution of prescriptions

Figure 2: Frequency of prescriptions of major groups of drugs

Conclusion

In this study, the average number of drugs per prescription was found to be 3.1, that was more than optimal range as per WHO/INRUD indicators was evident in this study. Polypharmacy can be reduced by rational drug prescription according to co-morbid conditions and strictly following the standard treatment guidelines. Overuse of antimicrobials was also found in this study but other prescription parameters such as prescription

of generic name, injectables prescribed and drugs prescribed among essential list of medicines were within ideal range as per WHO/INRUD indicators. Among antimicrobials, most commonly prescribed drugs were Amoxicillin + Clavulanic acid and cefixime and among NSAIDs, most commonly prescribed drugs were Ibuprofen + Paracetamol and Diclofenac. A constant watch should be kept on the medicines based on their consumption rate and pattern to avoid inadequacy or expiry of these medicines and necessary action for procurement,

storage and redistribution of drugs should be meticulously exercised.

Acknowledgement

Authors would like to acknowledge the guidance of Late Dr. Bhupendra Raj, Professor, and Dr. Vivek Pandey, Tutor, Department of Pharmacology for their guidance in this research work. Also, many thanks to Dr. S.P. Garg, then Medical Superintendent of the affiliated hospital for permitting us for data collection from the hospital.

References

1. Kumari R, Idris MZ, Bhushan V, Khanna A, Agrawal M, Singh SK. Assessment of prescription pattern at the public health facilities of Lucknow district. *Indian J Pharmacol.* Nov 2008; 40(6): 243-247.
2. World Health Organization. WHO/EDM/2002.3. Promoting Rational Use of Medicines: core components. WHO Policy and perspectives on medicine no. 5 Document Geneva: WHO; 2002.
3. Laing RO. Rational Drug Use: An Unsolved Problem. *Tropical Doctor.* 1990;20(3): 101-103.
4. Mittal N, Mittal R, Singh I, Shafiq N, Malhotra S. Drug Utilisation Study in a Tertiary Care Center: Recommendations for Improving Hospital Drug Dispensing Policies. *Indian J Pharm Sci* 2014;76(4):308-314.
5. Hussain S, Yadav SS, Sawlani KK, Khattri S. Assessment of drug prescribing pattern using world health organization indicators in a tertiary care teaching hospital. *Indian J Public Health.* Apr-Jun 2018; 62(2): 156-158.
6. Shanmugapriya S, Saravanan T, Rajee SS, Venkatrajan R, Thomas PM. Drug prescription pattern of outpatients in a tertiary care teaching hospital in Tamil Nadu. *Perspect Clin Res.* Jul-Sep 2018; 9(3): 133- 138.
7. Lalan BK, Hiray RS, Ghongane BB. Drug prescription pattern of outpatients in a tertiary care teaching hospital in Maharashtra. *Int J Pharm Bio Sci.* Jul 2012; 3(3): 225-229.
8. Mohanty BK, Aswini M, Hasamnis AA, Patil SS, Murty KS, Jena SK. Prescription pattern in the department of medicine of a tertiary care hospital in South India. *Journal of clinical and diagnostic research.* Feb 2010; 4(1): 2047-2051.
9. R Vaishnavi PR, Gaikwad N, Dhaneria SP. Assessment of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug use pattern using World Health Organization indicators: A cross-sectional study in a tertiary care teaching hospital of Chhattisgarh. *Indian J Pharmacol.* Nov-Dec 2017; 49(6): 445-450.
10. Madi L, Ahmed Elhada AH, Alrawashdeh H, Ahmed A. Prescribing Pattern of Proton Pump Inhibitors in Qatar Rehabilitation Institute: A Retrospective Study. *J Res Pharm Pract.* Apr-Jun 2019; 8(2):101-104.
11. Bilal AI, Osman ED, Mulugeta A. Assessment of medicines use pattern using World Health Organization's Prescribing, Patient Care and Health facility indicators in selected health facilities in eastern Ethiopia. *BMC Health Serv Res.* Apr 23 2016; 16: 144.
12. Datta S. Utilization Study of Antihypertensives in a South Indian Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital and Adherence to Standard Treatment Guidelines. *J Basic Clin Pharm.* Dec 2016; 8(1):33-37.
13. Yimer YS, Addis GT, Alemu MA. Evaluation of prescription completeness, rational drug-use patterns using WHO prescribing, patient-care and facility indicators in Debre Tabor Comprehensive Specialized Hospital, Ethiopia: A cross-sectional study. *SAGE Open Med.* Sep 2022; 6; 10: 20503121221122422.
14. Shrestha R, Prajapati S. Assessment of prescription pattern and prescription error in outpatient Department at Tertiary Care District Hospital, Central Nepal. *J Pharm Policy Pract.* Jul 2019; 10; 12: 16.
15. Atif M, Sarwar MR, Azeem M, Umer D, Rauf A, Rasool A, Ahsan M, Scahill S. Assessment of WHO/INRUD core drug use indicators in two tertiary care hospitals of Bahawalpur, Punjab, Pakistan. *J Pharm Policy Pract.* Sep 2016; 22(9): 27.
16. Ofori-Adjei YA, Fiakpornoo M. The influence of physicians' specialty on prescribing patterns at a general medicine out-patients clinic. *Ghana Med J.* Sep 2019; 53(3): 204-209.
17. Summoro TS, Gidebo KD, Kanche ZZ, Woticha EW. Evaluation of trends of drug-prescribing patterns based on WHO prescribing indicators at outpatient departments of four hospitals in southern Ethiopia. *Drug Des Devel Ther.* Aug 10, 2015; 9: 4551-4557.
18. Tripathy JP, Bahuguna P, Prinja S. Drug prescription behavior: A cross-sectional study in public health facilities in two states of North India. *Perspect Clin Res.* Apr-Jun 2018; 9(2): 76-82.
19. Ata, M., Hoque, R., Biswas, R. S. R., Mostafa, A., Hasan, F. U., & Barua, H. R. Antibiotics Prescribing Pattern at Outpatient Department of A Tertiary Medical College Hospital. *Chattagram Maa-O-Shishu Hospital Medical College Journal.* 2019; 17(2): 36-39.